

Unveiling the Kinetics of Oxygen Evolution Reaction in Defect-Engineered B/P-incorporated Cobalt-Oxide Electrocatalysts

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Abstract:

Defect-rich transition-metal oxide electrocatalysts hold great promise for alkaline water electrolysis due to their enhanced activity and stability. This study presents a new strategy that significantly improve the OER activity of Co-oxide nanosheets through incorporation of B and P (B/P-CoO_x NS), eventually leading to abundant surface defects and oxygen vacancies. The B/P-CoO_x NS demonstrate low overpotentials of 220 mV to achieve 10 mA cm⁻². The electrochemical and kinetic studies coupled with conventional morphological and structural characterizations, reveal that various crystalline defects like vacancies, dislocations, twin planes, and grain boundaries play crucial role in promoting the OH⁻ ion adsorption, the formation of intermediates, and the desorption of oxygen molecules. The industrial viability of the developed electrocatalyst is substantiated through assessments under harsh industrial conditions of 6 M KOH at 60 °C in a zero-gap single-cell alkaline electrolyzer which achieves 1 A cm⁻² at 1.95 V. Chronoamperometry tests (100 hours) highlight remarkable robustness of the electrocatalyst. This work establishes a new strategy to fabricate defect-rich OER electrocatalysts, setting a precedent to achieve better OER rates with non-noble materials.

Keywords:

water splitting, electrocatalyst, oxygen vacancy, crystalline defects, oxygen evolution reaction, kinetic study

1. Introduction:

Hydrogen, generated via water splitting through renewable energy sources, is a promising energy carrier, offering an alternative to conventional fossil fuel-based options owing to its high energy density and renewable nature.[1,2] The oxygen evolution reaction (OER), a pivotal step in this water-splitting process, involves multiple electron transfer stages which makes it a sluggish and energy-intensive process.[3] While highly active noble metal-based electrocatalysts like RuO₂ and IrO₂ are the benchmarks for OER,[4] their commercialization is impeded by their excessive cost resulting from scarcity. Consequently, there is a pressing need to develop an economically viable, highly active, and robust electrocatalyst for OER. Non-noble transition metal oxide (TMO)-based materials,[5,6] including perovskites,[7,8] layered hydroxides,[9,10] and spinels[3,11] have emerged as promising electrocatalysts for OER, especially for alkaline water electrolysis. TMOs are preferred owing to their exceptional stability, but their OER activity is limited by their inherent low conductivity. In recent years, there has been a growing emphasis on promoting the OER activity of TMOs through defect engineering without affecting their inherent stability.[12]

Crystal defects, such as grain boundaries, stacking faults, twin planes, edge and screw dislocations, etc. have been found to be actively participating in the water splitting to enhance the catalytic activity. [13] The presence of lattice defects such as vacancies contribute to the structural stability of TMOs under OER conditions by accommodating strain and lattice distortions.[14,15] These defects regulate the surface chemistry of TMOs, influencing the adsorption and desorption of reaction intermediates by affecting their binding energies during the OER[11]. Studies conducted by research groups have consistently reported that the presence of oxygen vacancies significantly improves the performance of the OER as observed in oxygen vacancy-rich Co₃O₄ and Cu(OH)₂. [11,16,17] Moreover, TMO with three-

dimensional defects such as pores can create pathways for ion diffusion improving the mass transport during the OER.

Several routes have been explored to introduce crystalline defects in TMOs, including chemical doping, high-temperature treatment, plasma engraving, ion-implantation, ball-milling, electrochemical methods, wet-chemical reduction methods, and hydrothermal/solvothermal synthesis.[18,19] Most of these methodologies have shown promise in improving the catalytic activity. For instance, metal-organic framework (MOF)-derived Co_3O_4 through calcination,[20] plasma-engraved Co_3O_4 nanosheet arrays[21,22], thin films of LaCoO_3 [23] and LaNiO_3 [8] perovskites synthesized using pulsed laser deposition have been demonstrated to exhibit enhanced OER performance due to defect engineering. Nevertheless, synthesizing a single material with multi-defective sites has been a challenging task with these techniques.

Also, despite the experimental advancements, the role of crystalline defects in catalyzing the OER has been relatively underexplored in the existing literature. Understanding the dynamic effects of defects on surface reconstruction during OER is crucial for understanding their role in the process. In recent literature, electrochemical studies have been employed to observe the in-situ progression of electrocatalytic reactions as demonstrated by Xiao et al., Doyle et al., and Li et al.[11,16,24]. These simple yet powerful techniques can provide insights into every step of the reaction mechanism, yet the detailed OER mechanism was rarely studied utilizing these techniques.

With an aim to develop multi-defect-rich TMO-based electrocatalysts, cobalt oxide nanosheets were synthesized by incorporating phosphorous and boron (B/P- CoO_x NS). A simple two-step hydrothermal-reduction process was utilized to synthesize the catalyst as opposed to the complex multi-step process mentioned in the literature. The resulting easy-to-synthesize material exhibited abundant multi-dimensional defect sites, which were investigated in detail

through different electrochemical and morphological techniques. In the literature, electrocatalysts incorporated with B or P show improved OER activity but their specific role is inadequately studied hence in the current work, the role of inclusion of both B and P was discovered to create multiple crystalline defects. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and cyclic voltammetry (CV) were utilized to investigate the complete kinetic behavior of the OER. Apart from routine 3-electrode measurements, the catalyst was evaluated in a 2-electrode assembly as well as in a single-cell water electrolyzer to establish its relevance for scale-up applications. The present work not only provides valuable insights into the facile synthesis of multi-defective TMO-based electrocatalysts but also sheds light on the dynamics of the OER on such surfaces that can be extended to other TMOs.

2. Material and methods:

2.1 Synthesis procedure of Co_3O_4 nanosheets:

The Co_3O_4 nanosheet (NS) catalyst was synthesized by a hydrothermal synthesis route adopted from our previous work.[3] Cobalt nitrate ($\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$), urea ($\text{Co}(\text{NH}_2)_2$), and sodium fluoride (NaF) were used as cobalt precursor, precipitating agent, and morphology controlling agent, respectively.[3] Typically, cobalt nitrate (1 mmol), urea (5 mmol), and NaF (3 mmol) were dissolved in 70 ml of deionized water and the resultant mixture was transferred to a 100 ml Teflon-lined steel autoclave. After sealing, the autoclave was kept in a hot air oven at 135 °C for 6 h to obtain nanosheet morphology. Later, the autoclave was cooled naturally, and the pink-colored precipitate was extracted which was washed several times with deionized water and ethanol to remove the unwanted byproducts. Finally, the washed precipitate was dried at 80 °C for 1 h followed by calcination in a muffle furnace at 300 °C for 3 h to obtain Co_3O_4 NS in the form of black powder.

2.2 Incorporation of B and P in Co₃O₄ nanosheets:

To incorporate boron (B) and phosphorus (P) into Co₃O₄ NS, a chemical reduction method was employed using sodium borohydride (NaBH₄) and sodium hypophosphite (NaH₂PO₂·H₂O) as reducing agents as well as sources of B and P, respectively. Initially, Co₃O₄ NS was dispersed in 25 ml of deionized water under ultrasonication for 5 min. Subsequently, NaH₂PO₂ was added to the solution followed by 25 ml aqueous solution of NaBH₄ under constant stirring for 12 h until the bubble generation ceased. The total weight ratio of reducing agents (NaBH₄ and NaH₂PO₂) to the Co₃O₄ NS was maintained constant at 60, while the molar ratio of NaBH₄ to NaH₂PO₂ (B/P ratio) was varied (1, 4, and 7) to obtain different compositions of the electrocatalyst. The resulting black-colored mixture was separated using centrifugation and washed thoroughly with deionized water and ethanol. For reference, B incorporated Co₃O₄ NS was also prepared by using only NaBH₄ during the reduction reaction. On the contrary, when NaH₂PO₂ was used as the sole reducing agent, P was not incorporated in Co₃O₄ NS owing to its weak nature as a reducing agent.

2.3 Electrochemical characterizations:

All the electrochemical tests were conducted using a Gamry (Interface 5000E) electrochemical workstation in a typical three-electrode setup. A glassy carbon electrode (GCE) with a 3 mm diameter (Gamry Instruments) served as the working electrode. For catalyst loading, a homogeneous ink was prepared by sonicating 3 mg of catalyst powder in 1 ml of ethanol for 10 min. Additionally, a separate binder solution was prepared by mixing 20 µl of Nafion in 0.5 ml of ethanol and sonicated for 1 min. A 10 µl of binder solution followed by 10 µl of catalyst ink was sequentially deposited onto the GCE and dried quickly under an infrared lamp to obtain the catalyst loading of 0.4 mg cm⁻². For the electrochemical measurements, an Hg/HgO reference electrode and a graphite rod counter electrode were used in 1M KOH electrolyte.

Prior to any measurements, 10 repeated linear sweep voltammograms (LSV) were recorded in the anodic potential range of 0 to 0.8 V (vs. Hg/HgO) at a scan rate of 2 mV s⁻¹ to condition the catalyst surface and to obtain pre-oxidation peaks. All subsequent LSVs were obtained at the same scan rate of 2 mV s⁻¹. Constant stirring of the electrolyte was maintained to eliminate bubbles from the GCE surface and enhance mass transfer. To ensure consistency, all measured potentials were converted with respect to the reversible hydrogen electrode (vs RHE). This conversion was achieved by adding the value of 0.924 V, determined according to the Nernst equation $E_{(RHE)} = E^0_{(Hg/HgO)} + 0.059 \cdot \text{pH}$, where $E^0_{(Hg/HgO)} = 0.098$ V, and pH = 14 for 1 M KOH. Additional details regarding electrochemical characterizations are provided in the supporting information.

3. Results and discussion:

3.1. Structural and morphological characterizations:

The cobalt oxide nanosheet (Co₃O₄ NS) catalyst was synthesized using the hydrothermal method, followed by annealing in air. Later, Co₃O₄ NS was incorporated with B and P by chemical reduction method using corresponding reducing agents. Various B/P ratios of 1, 4, and 7 were used to optimize the stoichiometry of the non-metals in Co₃O₄ NS. The OER overpotential values recorded at 10 mA cm⁻² were used as a metric to screen the optimal B/P ratio (**Figure S1a**).

As per the catalytic performance (discussed later), the B/P ratio of 4 was found to be the best for OER, and henceforth, this catalyst is designated as B/P-CoO_x NS. Along with pristine Co₃O₄ NS and B/P-CoO_x NS, B-incorporated Co₃O₄ NS (B-Co₃O₄ NS) was also investigated as a reference catalyst. P-Co₃O₄ was also synthesized by using only NaH₂PO₂ but it appeared that P could not get incorporated into Co₃O₄ structure in the absence of a strong reducing agent like NaBH₄. This was further confirmed by comparing its catalytic activity, XRD, and Raman

spectra with pristine Co_3O_4 NS where no appreciable change was observed (**Figure S2**). Thus, the P- Co_3O_4 catalyst is not discussed further.

Figure 1: (a), (b), (c) SEM images; (d), (e), (f) and (g), (h), (i) TEM micrographs; (j), (k), (l)

HRTEM micrographs of Co_3O_4 NS, B- Co_3O_4 NS, and B/P- CoO_x NS, respectively.

SEM images confirmed the formation of 2D-nanosheets for pristine Co_3O_4 NS (**Figure 1a**), which were well maintained even after the introduction of B and B/P, as evident in **Figure 1b, c**, respectively. The lateral thickness of NS (~ 60 nm) was maintained throughout the catalyst with the planar width varied in the range of 5 to 20 μm . The surface morphology of NS was very rough for B/P- CoO_x NS (**Figure 1c**) in comparison to the other two electrocatalysts which appeared smooth. TEM images (**Figure 1d-f**) confirmed the nanosheet morphology, though it is noteworthy that the constituent building blocks forming these nanosheets were different for each catalyst. The pristine Co_3O_4 NS (**Figure 1g**) comprises irregularly shaped particles larger than ~ 20 nm, whereas the B-incorporated Co_3O_4 NS (**Figure 1h**) is composed of quadrilateral-shaped particles with an average diagonal of ~ 15 nm. In contrast, the B/P- CoO_x NS visibly exhibits spherical particles with an average diameter of ~ 5 nm (**Figure 1i**). The lattice spacing of 0.46 nm corresponding to the (111) plane of spinal Co_3O_4 is visible in Co_3O_4 NS and B- Co_3O_4 NS (**Figure 1j, k**).^[3,25] On the contrary, B/P- CoO_x NS showed a lattice spacing of 0.23 nm attributed to the (111) plane of the CoO phase^[26] (**Figure 1l**).

The formation of ripples (**Figure 1l**) and similar defects were detected in the majority of B/P- CoO_x NS through HRTEM (**Figure S3a-e**). Atomic scale STEM images of B/P- CoO_x NS (**Figure 2 and S3**) revealed the presence of abundant crystalline linear defects such as grain boundaries (white line) separating different grains of the CoO phase (**Figure 2a and S3f**). The presence of multiple edge dislocations (area marked within a red line in **Figure 2b and S3g**) was also noticed along with deformation (**Figure 2b, S3h**) indicated by the red arrow. These edge dislocations of **Figure 2c** were further strain mapped by geometric phase analysis (GPA) and presented in **Figure 2d**. The straining of crystal at edge dislocation sites can be clearly depicted in the strain map denoted by white arrows. Another prominent planar defects, like twin planes, are also visible in the nanoparticles (**Figure S3i**), where its magnified portion

(marked as a black square) is shown in **Figure 2e**. The corresponding strain map (**Figure 2f**) displays the strain along these twin planes (white arrows).

Figure 2: Atomic resolution STEM images of B/P-CoO_x NS with (a) different crystal grains, (b,c) edge dislocations, (d) strain map of (c), (e) twinning planes, and (f) corresponding strain map.

A strong reducing agent like NaBH₄ reduces metal ions to decrease their oxidation state by forming oxygen vacancy defects to maintain charge neutrality.[18] The addition of anions like P can further increase the formation of defects due to their lower/negative oxidation state.[18,19] Additionally, the larger ionic radius of P compared to B (and Co) introduces a higher degree of defects and structural distortions. Thus, during the exothermic reduction of Co-oxide, due to the use of a high amount of reducing agents and a longer time of reaction, the crystal structure gets transformed from Co₃O₄ to CoO, producing various defects. Such strain-

induced defect sites are highly beneficial for the OER as lattice strain causes shifting in the d-band center that directly results in optimal binding strength of adsorbate to the active sites.[12,14,15,18,19,27]

Figure 3: (a) XRD pattern, and (b) Raman spectra of Co_3O_4 NS, $\text{B-Co}_3\text{O}_4$ NS, and B/P-CoO_x NS.

The XRD pattern of both pristine Co_3O_4 NS and $\text{B-Co}_3\text{O}_4$ NS (**Figure 3a**) exhibits prominent peaks of spinel Co_3O_4 phase as shown in **Table S1**. [3,25,28] Conversely, B/P-CoO_x NS with B/P ratio 1 showed a broad hump at 45° (**Figure S4**) corresponding to the amorphous CoPB phase, as seen from the XRD pattern of amorphous CoPB powder (**Figure S4**). The broad hump at 45° is a characteristic feature observed in many amorphous cobalt phospho-borides powders which occurs due to the presence of short-range ordering and long-range disordering. [4,29,30]

The B/P ratios 4 and 7 exhibit peaks of CoO , respectively (**Table S1**). [25,31,32] This finding suggests that when only B is used as a reducing agent, as in $\text{B-Co}_3\text{O}_4$, the Co_3O_4 phase was retained while upon the addition of P, in $\text{B/P} = 1$, the structure becomes amorphous and then recrystallizes to CoO , with higher ratios.

This confirms the complete structural transformation from Co_3O_4 to CoO upon the joint incorporation of both B and P. Moreover, the peak position of B/P-CoO_x NS is shifted to higher

2θ values by 0.4° , indicating the lattice strain resulting from the introduction of both non-metals, as also evident from the STEM analysis. In Raman spectra (**Figure 3b**), pristine Co_3O_4 NS and B- Co_3O_4 NS exhibited bands around 479, 521, and 680 cm^{-1} , assigned to the E_{2g} , F_{2g} , and A_{1g} phonon modes of the Co_3O_4 phase.[33] In contrast, B/P- CoO_x NS displayed two prominent bands around 547 and 680 cm^{-1} accompanied by a shoulder band at 480 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the E_g , T_{2g} , and A_{1g} phonon modes, respectively, of the fcc-CoO phase.[33] The peak broadening is observed in B- Co_3O_4 NS and B/P- CoO_x NS compared to the as-prepared Co_3O_4 NS which signifies structural modifications on the catalyst surface. This transformation from Co_3O_4 to the CoO phase and the broadening of peaks indicates a substantial alteration in the O and Co coordination in B/P- CoO_x NS, which resulted in the emergence of numerous defects within the structure.

Figure S5 presents the BET isotherms for B/P- CoO_x NS, B- Co_3O_4 NS, and Co_3O_4 NS with specific areas determined as 2.7, 30.2, and $36.2\text{ m}^2\text{ g}^{-1}$, respectively. The significant change in the surface area of B/P- CoO_x NS compared to Co_3O_4 NS and B- Co_3O_4 NS is attributed to the structural and morphological variations during the reduction reaction. This decrease is also attributed to the relatively packed structure of B/P- CoO_x NS compared to the porous nature of the other two catalysts, observed in TEM images (**Figure 1g-i**). The elemental mapping (**Figure S6**) of B/P- CoO_x NS illustrates the presence and uniform distribution of Co, B, P, and O in the catalyst. From XPS, the B/P molar ratio for B/P- CoO_x NS was obtained to be 4.6. In the Co 2p level (**Figure 4a**), for Co_3O_4 NS (**Figure 4a upper panel**), the peak of $\text{Co}2p_{3/2}$ was deconvoluted into two peaks centered at 779.5 and 780.7 eV, along with the satellite peaks at 785.0 and 789.2 eV, assigned to Co^{3+} and Co^{2+} species, respectively, of Co_3O_4 . [3,34] Both the corresponding peaks are also evident in the other spin-orbit component $2p_{1/2}$ along with satellite peaks. The intensity ratio of these Co^{3+} and Co^{2+} signals is retained for B- Co_3O_4 NS (**Figure 4a middle panel**) but the peak position is negatively shifted by 0.3 eV to 779.2 and 780.4 eV,

respectively, with respect to pristine Co_3O_4 NS. On the contrary, the peak intensity ratio of Co^{2+} to Co^{3+} increases considerably for B/P- CoO_x NS (**Figure 4a bottom panel**) compared to Co_3O_4 NS with a negative shift in peak positions (779.3 and 780.4 eV), thus again confirming the surface transformation to form CoO phase. The spectra of the B 1s and P 2p levels (**Figure 4b, c**) reveal both elements were predominantly present in the oxidized states.[4,34] Small peaks corresponding to Co-B (187.9 eV) and Co-P bonds (129.0 eV) were also visible for B/P- CoO_x NS.[35,36] The prominent peaks in the O 1s region were deconvoluted in three peaks for pristine Co_3O_4 NS (**Figure 4d upper panel**), with a dominant peak centered at 529.7 eV corresponding to oxygen in the Co_3O_4 crystal lattice ($\text{O}_{\text{lattice}}$); while the other two minor peaks at 530.9 and 532.8 eV are assigned to OH^- group and water molecules adsorbed on the surface.[11,18,19] By incorporation of only B, a new peak emerges at 531.5 eV, with an intensity comparable to the $\text{O}_{\text{lattice}}$ at 529.5 eV (**Figure 4d middle panel**). This new signal is assigned to the oxygen in the hydroxyl group attached to the uncoordinated oxygen vacancy sites (O_v). As emphasized in recent articles[37,38] the peak at 531.5 eV is not the direct interpretation of O_v but of OH^- species attached to O_v . As oxygen defects on the surface are unstable, they rapidly “heal” by adsorption of OH^- species and hence the peak at 531.5 eV is indirectly connected to the amount of O_v or defects on the surface. Upon the inclusion of both B and P in Co_3O_4 NS (**Figure 4d bottom panel**), the peak due to $\text{O}_{\text{lattice}}$ at 529.3 eV diminishes significantly leaving the peak of O_v at 531.5 eV as the most dominant peak. This again proves the surface transformation where metal-oxygen bonds are replaced with non-metal (B or P) bonds. Most importantly, the presence of O_v (in the form of adsorbed OH^-) is predominant on the surface of the B/P- CoO_x NS electrocatalyst. All the above findings reveal that just B-introduction does not affect the Co_3O_4 phase, but it produces oxygen vacancies which leads to electron modulation around Co. On the other hand, the surface Co_3O_4 phase completely transforms into the CoO phase by the introduction of both B and P, which also provides an

abundant amount of oxygen vacancies and forms the bonds of Co not only with O but with P and B on the surface.

Figure 4: High-resolution XPS spectra of (a) Co 2p, (b) B 1s, (c) P 2p, and (d) O 1s levels, and (e) ESR spectra for pristine Co_3O_4 NS, $\text{B-Co}_3\text{O}_4$ NS, and B/P-CoO_x NS

To validate the occurrence of O_v , an EPR analysis was conducted which can detect the trapped unpaired electrons left behind by oxygen when it leaves the crystal to form an O_v . [19] The first derivative EPR spectra of all the electrocatalysts (**Figure 4e**) reveal a typical signal at g-values (where intensity is 0) of 2.1, indicative of unpaired electrons [39] thus confirming the formation of O_v and defects. Notably, B/P-CoO_x NS exhibits the highest intensity of the EPR signal,

followed by B-Co₃O₄ NS and Co₃O₄ NS. This implies that boron introduces O_v in the pristine Co₃O₄ NS, and phosphorus further enhances the number of O_v in conjunction with boron, confirming the XPS results.

3.2. Electrochemical characterizations:

To assess the electrocatalytic performance of the electrocatalysts, linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) curves were recorded (**Figure 5a**), and the overpotential at the benchmark current density of 10 mA cm⁻² (η_{10}) was used as a parameter for comparison. Initially, the B/P ratio was varied (1, 4, and 7) to find the optimal stoichiometry of B and P in Co₃O₄ NS (**Figure S1a**).

The B/P ratio of 4 exhibited the lowest η_{10} value of 220 mV followed by the B/P ratio of 7 with η_{10} value of 240 mV. However, the electrocatalyst with an equal amount of B and P was found to be inactive for the OER, thus emphasizing the requirement of optimal concentration of B and P in Co₃O₄ NS. Upon comparing with the counterparts, η_{10} of B/P-CoO_x NS is significantly lower than B-Co₃O₄ NS (290 mV), Co₃O₄ NS (400 mV), and the traditional benchmark RuO₂ (370 mV). To ensure the repeatability of the results, the electrochemical measurements were repeated twice on different samples and both yielded similar data (**Figure S1b**). Even at 100 mA cm⁻², an overpotential of 298 mV is required by B/P-CoO_x NS. This value is lower than some of the best transition metal oxide-based OER catalysts, including NiFe LDH[40,41] (**Table S2**).

A few electrocatalysts report even lower overpotential values but it must be noted that they utilize significantly higher amounts of catalyst loading (5-10 mg cm⁻²) on porous substrates (Ni foam, carbon cloth, Ti-mesh), making a direct comparison unreasonable.[5,42–44] To address this discrepancy arising from different catalyst loading, the mass activity of several catalysts is assessed and compared to that of B/P-CoO_x NS at an overpotential of 270 mV as depicted in

Figure 5b. The mass activity (**Figure S7**) has increased substantially by 200 times after incorporating B and P in Co_3O_4 NS (92.3 A g^{-1}) as compared to pristine Co_3O_4 NS (0.43 A g^{-1}) at an overpotential of 270 mV. The Tafel slopes were determined to be 51 mV dec^{-1} , 67 mV dec^{-1} , 66 mV dec^{-1} , and 90 mV dec^{-1} for B/P- CoO_x NS, B- Co_3O_4 NS, Co_3O_4 NS, and RuO_2 , respectively (**Figure 5c**). The lowest Tafel slope observed for B/P- CoO_x NS indicates faster OER kinetics compared to the reference electrocatalysts. Nyquist plot (**Figure 5d**) illustrated that the B/P- CoO_x NS exhibits the lowest charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) of 2.7Ω in comparison to B- Co_3O_4 NS (3.3Ω) and Co_3O_4 NS (12.5Ω).

Figure 5: (a) Anodic polarization curves, (b) Plot of comparison of mass activity with state-of-the-art TM electrocatalysts, (c) Tafel plots, (d) Nyquist plots at 1.5 V vs RHE, (e) Plot of ΔJ (at OCP) vs scan rate for B/P- CoO_x NS, B- Co_3O_4 NS, Co_3O_4 NS, and RuO_2 in 1M KOH.

The improved charge transfer across electrolyte and electrode is attributed to an abundant amount of O_v , where, during its formation, the electron left behind is transferred to the conduction band to increase the conductivity,[18] in contrast to poorly conducting Co_3O_4 . Moreover, metal borides and phospho-borides are known for their metallic character[4,45] and the incorporation of B/P may increase the metallicity of Co_3O_4 NS, thereby further improving its conductivity. The double-layer capacitance (C_{dl}) values reported in **Figure 5e** were obtained from CV curves (**Figure S8**) and were used to determine the electrochemically active surface area (ECSA). The ECSA of B/P- CoO_x NS was around 350 cm^2 ($C_{dl} = 14\text{ mF cm}^{-2}$), which is considerably higher than 62.5 cm^2 and 15 cm^2 achieved for B- Co_3O_4 NS ($C_{dl} = 2.5\text{ mF cm}^{-2}$) and pristine Co_3O_4 NS ($C_{dl} = 0.6\text{ mF cm}^{-2}$), respectively (**Table S3**). Despite a low specific surface area, the ECSA of B/P- CoO_x NS is much higher, indicating the formation of dense active sites that can be directly related to the multiple defects and O_v . To determine the intrinsic activity of individual active sites, turnover frequency (TOF) was calculated as a function of applied potential (**Figure S9a**). The high TOF values for B/P- CoO_x NS at any applied potential compared to B- Co_3O_4 NS and Co_3O_4 NS indicate superior intrinsic activity per site. To illustrate this fact further, the specific activity of the electrocatalysts can be examined by plotting the LSV with current normalized by BET surface area (**Figure S9b**). This plot eliminates the contribution from the specific surface area for different samples and considers only the contributions of active sites. From the figure, it is evident that B/P- CoO_x NS has superior catalytic performance owing to the formation of a large number of dense active sites with significantly high intrinsic activity. Thus, the impressive OER activity for B and P incorporated Co_3O_4 NS is attributed to improved charge transfer, number of active sites, and intrinsic activity, due to the presence of defects and O_v . Typically, in catalysts, defects such as lattice dislocations and twin planes can generate a stress field around them, which in turn

modulates the electronic structure of the elements on the surface to make them active for adsorption and desorption of the reactant and the products.[14,27]

3.3. Kinetic studies and post-OER characterizations:

In order to understand the role played by these defects and O_v in OER, the kinetics of the reaction were investigated through in-situ electrochemical measurements. OER mechanism involves the adsorption of OH^- ions on transition metal sites (M-OH) followed by the formation of M-O, M-OOH intermediates and the deprotonation to form M-O₂ followed by O₂ desorption (**Equation S1-5**).[3] As OER and surface transformation occur simultaneously, each step can be investigated by in-situ kinetic studies for OER which also reveals the dynamic evolution of the surface active sites on the electrocatalyst.

To investigate the adsorption of OH^- ions (**Equation S1**), EIS was recorded at different applied potentials (1.24-1.79 V vs RHE) (**Figure S10a, b, c**).[11,16] The obtained Nyquist plots with three merged semicircles (illustrated in **Schematic S1**) were fitted with the circuit consisting of three parallel RC circuits (**Schematic S2**). The first RC circuit with charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) at the electrolyte-electrode interface and C_{dl} gives rise to the first semicircle, while the second semicircle arises due to parallel circuit of R_{film} and C_{film} belonging to the resistance and dielectric properties of the underlying oxide film.[16]

The third semicircle is matched with the circuit consisting of R_{OH} and C_{OH} connected to the resistance and pseudo-capacitance of OH^- adsorption. Thus, the first and third semicircles show the properties of the surface, while the second semicircle gives an idea about the bulk of the film. The values of the resistances and capacitances after fitting the Nyquist spectra of all the electrocatalysts (**Figure S10a, b, c**) are presented in **Table S4**. The R_{ct} values of B/P-CoO_x NS are lower than B-Co₃O₄ NS and Co₃O₄ NS, highlighting the better charge transfer at the interface as observed earlier.

Figure 6: (a) Plots of C_{OH} vs potential, (b) log of R_{OH} vs potential, (c) Slow scan linear polarization curves, (d) Post-OER Raman spectra of B/P- CoO_x NS, B-Co₃O₄ NS and Co₃O₄ NS, High-resolution post-OER XPS spectra of (e) Co 2p, (f) O 1s, (g) B 1s and (h) P 2p levels of B/P-CoO_x, (i) Bode plots at 1.54 V, (j) Cyclic voltammograms, (k) Plots of half difference between redox peaks in CV vs \ln of scan rate for B/P-CoO_x NS, B-Co₃O₄ NS, and Co₃O₄ NS.

For all the electrocatalysts, the value of R_{OH} decreases, and C_{OH} increases as potential is increased. This indicates that as potential increases, OH^- adsorption rate increases and it accumulates around the surface active sites.[11]

To quantify the OH^- adsorption, the charge (Q_{OH}) connected to it was computed by integrating the plot of C_{OH} vs potential (**Figure 6a**). The highest Q_{OH} value achieved for B/P- CoO_x NS (337 μC) compared to B- Co_3O_4 NS (146 μC) and Co_3O_4 NS (103 μC) demonstrates the enhanced OH^- adsorption over the surface of B/P- CoO_x NS attributed to the electronically modulated metal active sites surrounded by large number of defects and O_v . The presence of O_v increases the energy gap between the highest occupied d-state (E_d) and fermi level (E_F), resulting in the improved binding of intermediates at the active sites.[18] By linearly fitting the plots of $\log(R_{OH})$ vs potential, the EIS-based Tafel slopes were determined (**Figure 6b**) which are more precise as they are obtained under steady-state conditions.[46] B/P- CoO_x NS, B- Co_3O_4 NS, and Co_3O_4 NS showed the Tafel slopes of 47 $mV\ dec^{-1}$, 61 $mV\ dec^{-1}$, and 64 $mV\ dec^{-1}$, respectively, again showcasing the better kinetics for OH^- adsorption over B/P- CoO_x NS. After the adsorption of OH^- ions, the formation of subsequent M-O, M-OOH, and M- O_2 intermediates (**Equation S2,3,4**) were investigated by examining the pre-oxidation peaks.[3,11] The LSV (2 $mV\ s^{-1}$) in the first OER cycle of the fresh electrocatalysts was probed to understand the progressive formation of intermediates (**Figure 6c**). All the electrocatalysts show first peaks in the potential range of 1.1 to 1.25 V corresponding to Co^{2+} to Co^{3+} (related to **Equation S3**) conversion indicating the formation of Co-OOH intermediate. The next peak in the range of 1.25 to 1.45 depicts the Co^{3+} to Co^{4+} conversion (**Equation S4**) resulting from the formation of the Co- O_2 intermediate.[3] The highest peak intensity of pre-oxidation peaks for B/P- CoO_x NS is directly indicative of a large number of Co-OOH and Co- O_2 species formation in this catalyst compared to other catalysts.

As per post-OER Raman spectra (**Figure 6d**), the dominant vibrational peak connected to the CoO phase drastically decreases while maintaining the A1g (666 cm^{-1}) peak of the B/P-CoO_x NS electrocatalyst. This is the partial evidence of reconstruction on the surface facilitated by the presence of imperfections.[47] Raman bands in B-Co₃O₄ NS and pristine Co₃O₄ NS showed no major changes compared to their pre-OER spectra, indicating reconstruction is limited due to the formation of a smaller number of active sites. To further elaborate on the surface reconstruction, post-OER XPS was performed on the B/P-CoO_x NS. The peak of Co²⁺ (781.8) exceedingly decreased while the peak at 780.6 eV corresponding to Co-OOH appears with high intensity (**Figure 6e**), thus confirming the surface reconstruction by the formation of Co-OOH active sites.[4] For O 1s spectra, peaks belonging to O_v, O_{lattice}, and adsorbed oxygen species are maintained with O_v (531.0 eV) dominating the O_{lattice} (529.6 eV) (**Figure 6f**). The oxidation peak of B and P is also maintained but the peak corresponding to Co-B and Co-P diminishes after OER (**Figure 6g,h**). Thus, Raman, XPS, and LSV analysis imply that the presence of various defects and O_v promotes the generation of a significant quantity of active Co-OOH species.

The deprotonation of Co-OOH species to form Co-O₂ (**Equation S4**) that leads to desorption of O₂ (**Equation S5**) can also be assessed using Bode plots obtained from EIS (**Figure S10d, e, f**). **Figure 6i** presents the Bode plot of the electrocatalysts recorded at a potential of 1.54 V (vs. RHE) for comparison, as at all other potentials the Bode plot exhibits similar behavior. The phase peak at higher (10^6 - 10^4 Hz) and middle (1 - 10^4 Hz) frequency ranges arise due to the surface oxidized species of Co-O₆ and Co-O₄, respectively[11] while the phase peak at the lowest frequency (1 - 0.01 Hz) is attributed to the deprotonation of Co-OOH.[11] The intensity of all three phase peaks is lower for B/P-CoO_x NS than B-Co₃O₄ NS, and Co₃O₄ NS, showcasing faster deprotonation.[48] The O₂ desorption step following deprotonation of Co-OOH was studied by Laviron analysis[11,49] involving measurement of CV curves in anodic

potential range at incremental scan rates. **Figure S10g, h, i** depicts the CV curves for all three catalysts recorded at increasing scan rates from 50 to 250 mV s^{-1} . For comparison, CV curves of all the electrocatalysts measured at a scan rate of 50 mV s^{-1} are shown in **Figure 6j**. Each of the electrocatalysts exhibits a reduction peak corresponding to the conversion of Co^{4+} back to Co^{3+} , indicating a reversible process. However, the absence of a peak for the Co^{3+} to Co^{2+} conversion implies the irreversible nature of this particular species. Due to this irreversible surface reconstruction, -OOH species were detected on the catalyst surface by Raman and XPS measurements after OER. The redox constant (k_s) was determined by linearly fitting the plot of the difference between the redox peak of $\text{Co}^{3+}/\text{Co}^{4+}$ vs \ln of scan rate (**Figure 6k**) and employing the Laviron equation[50] (**Equation S6**). As the $\text{Co}^{3+}/\text{Co}^{4+}$ redox peaks were used for the analysis, k_s represents the formation of the product in the form of an O_2 molecule after deprotonation of Co-OOH to Co-O_2 . The k_s value is maximum for B/P- CoO_x NS (0.42 s^{-1}) which is 3.8 and 5 times higher than B- Co_3O_4 NS (0.11 s^{-1}) and Co_3O_4 NS (0.08 s^{-1}), respectively, suggesting effective desorption of O_2 from the surface sites. The comprehensive kinetic study illustrates that electronic modulation created around Co through the presence of defects and O_v helps to improve the OH^- adsorption, facilitate deprotonation, and expedite O_2 desorption, finally resulting in better OER rates.

3.4. Electrochemical studies in industrial conditions:

Though 3-electrode measurements are crucial for studying the half-cell reactions over the catalysts, testing them under industrially relevant conditions is equally vital for practical applications. Industrial electrolysis typically employs a highly alkaline solution (such as 6M KOH) at elevated temperatures ($\sim 80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). Also, electrolysis is usually conducted at high current densities ($1\text{--}2 \text{ A cm}^{-2}$) using a two-electrode assembly where catalysts are coated on a conductive support like NF, which also acts as the gas diffusion layer. To mimic such conditions, B/P- CoO_x NS was deposited on NF and used as an anode in a 2-electrode assembly.

Different concentrations of electrolytes such as 1 M KOH, 6 M KOH, and 6 M KOH @80 °C were used. Moreover, no post-iR correction was performed to the data while calculating the overpotentials.

Figure 7: Two electrode linear polarization curves of B/P-CoO_x NS/NF (a) with Pt-mesh as a cathode in 1M KOH, 6M KOH, and 6M KOH at 80 °C, (b) with Pt-mesh and CoPB/NF as a cathode, (c) chronoamperometric stability test for 100 h, (d) Multistep stability test, (e) linear polarization curves before and after 10,000 cycles, chronoamperometric and step stability test, (f) Linear sweep voltammograms of CoPB/NF||B/P-CoO_x NS/NF and NF||NF assembly for comparison in zero-gap alkaline electrolyzer setup in 6 M KOH.

With a Pt mesh cathode, Pt || B/P-CoO_x NS/NF assembly could reach an ultra-high current density of 2 A cm⁻² at the cell potential of 3.00 V, 2.24 V, 1.95 V in 1 M KOH, 6 M KOH and 6 M KOH @ 80 °C, respectively (**Figure 7a**). In our previous work, an amorphous CoPB electrocatalyst was reported as a highly active HER catalyst.[4] Hence, B/P-CoO_x NS was also paired with amorphous CoPB on NF (CoPB/NF) in a two-electrode system to realize a

completely noble-metal-free system. Notably, the CoPB/NF||B/P-CoO_x NS/NF system (**Figure 7b**) required a cell potential of 2.83 V to achieve 2 A cm⁻² in 6 M KOH. A stability test was performed by applying a constant potential of 1.95 V across Pt||B/P-CoO_x NS/NF reaching a current density of 600 mA cm⁻² (**Figure 7c**) in 6 M KOH. The assembly demonstrated considerable stability with only a 14% decline in the current density over a period of 100 hrs, with a nominal degradation rate of 0.8 mA h⁻¹.

To realize the production of green hydrogen, electrocatalysts should be able to sustain the constantly fluctuating energy input from renewable energy sources. To mimic the electrocatalytic performance of Pt||B/P-CoO_x/NF NS in variable power, a multi-step chronoamperometric test was carried out in 6M KOH (**Figure 7d**). The results depict that the current density remained stable during rising and descending steps in the whole range of 0.125 A cm⁻² to 2 A cm⁻² (cell potential range of 1.73 to 2.24 V). Moreover, current densities at the same potential in the incremental and decremental steps are invariant. The LSVs were consistent after the constant-current and variable-current stability test as that of the initial LSV (**Figure 7e**). To test the robustness of the Pt||B/P-CoO_x NS/NF for multiple cycles of usage, recyclability testing for 10,000 cycles was performed in 6M KOH (**Figure 7e**). The cell potential was maintained even after 10,000 cycles at high current density indicating remarkable robustness. Pt||B/P-CoO_x NS/NF yielded an overall Faradaic efficiency of 97% (**Figure S11**) ascertaining very little loss of energy in the system. Finally, an alkaline electrolyzer setup with a working area of 5 cm² was constructed using B/P-CoO_x NS/NF as an anode and CoPB/NF as a cathode along with Zirfon membrane as a separator. **Figure 7f** shows the typical LSVs of CoPB/NF||B/P-CoO_x NS/NF along with NF||NF at room temperature and 60 °C in 6 M KOH. At room temperature, the cell potential of CoPB/NF||B/P-CoO_x NS/NF at 1A cm⁻² in zero-gap assembly (**Figure 7f**) is 2.12 V which is lower than that for bulk electrolyzer setup (**Figure 7b**) having cell potential of 2.33 V. The CoPB/NF||B/P-CoO_x NS/NF assembly could achieve the

high current density of 1 A cm^{-2} at 1.95 V at $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, demonstrating their relevance in zero-gap assembly as well.

4. Conclusion:

In summary, B and P incorporated cobalt oxide nanosheets are explored as highly active OER catalysts exhibiting remarkably low overpotentials of 220 mV and 298 mV at 10 and 100 mA cm^{-2} , respectively. Structural investigations unveil the complete transformation of the catalyst from the Co_3O_4 to the CoO phase due to the concomitant incorporation of B and P. This leads to a large number of linear defects in the crystal lattice, subsequently resulting in strained sites that serve as catalytic centers for OER. Further investigations confirm the formation of oxygen vacancies that not only act as OH^- absorption sites but also improve the conductivity of the oxide catalyst. Detailed electrochemical, kinetic, and post-OER studies help in analyzing each reaction step and how they are facilitated by the B/P- CoO_x NS catalyst. The considerable catalyst stability observed under a 2-electrode setup defines the relevance of B/P- CoO_x NS for industrial applications. Finally, in an all-non-noble catalyst assembly tested in a 5 cm^2 single-cell alkaline electrolyzer, a current density of 1 A cm^{-2} is achieved at a moderate cell potential of 1.95 V at $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, further underlining its potential for incorporation in scaled-up systems.

Conflict of Interest:

The authors declare no conflict of interest

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Appendix A. Supplementary data:

The following is the Supplementary data to this article:

Data availability:

Data will be made available on request.

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